

Supplemental Table S3

Summary of primary antibodies used in illustrations.

		Primary antibody (category number)	Dilution	Color code	
Figure 1	panel B, D, E, G	glucagon (ab10988)	1: 100	Magenta	
		insulin-Alexa Fluor® 488 (sc-8033_AF488)	1: 100	Blue	
		CK7 (ab68459)	1: 100	Green	
Figure 3	panel D, E, K-N, P	glucagon (ab10988)	1: 100	Magenta	
		insulin-Alexa Fluor® 488 (sc-8033_AF488)	1: 100	Blue	
		CK7 (ab68459)	1: 100	Green	
Figure 4	panel B'-D'	chromogranin A (61-0015)	1: 400	Brown	
	panel H-J	PGP9.5 (ab108986)	1: 100	Cyan	
	panel K, L	Ki-67 (61-0078)	1: 800	Brown	
	panel P, Q	glucagon (ab10988)	1: 100	Magenta	
		insulin-Alexa Fluor® 488 (sc-8033_AF488)	1: 100	Blue	
		CK7 (ab68459)	1: 100	Green	
Figure 5	panel B, E, H	glucagon (ab10988)	1: 100	Magenta	
		insulin-Alexa Fluor® 488 (sc-8033_AF488)	1: 100	Blue	
		CK7 (ab68459)	1: 100	Green	
Suppl. Fig. S1	panel B, D, F, H, J, L	glucagon (ab10988)	1: 100	Magenta	
		insulin-Alexa Fluor® 488 (sc-8033_AF488)	1: 100	Blue	
		CK7 (ab68459)	1: 100	Green	
Suppl. Fig. S3	panel D	glucagon (ab10988)	1: 100	Magenta	
		insulin-Alexa Fluor® 488 (sc-8033_AF488)	1: 100	Blue	
		CK7 (ab68459)	1: 100	Green	
	panel E	PGP9.5 (ab108986)	1: 100	Cyan	
		CD31 (MS-353-S1)	1: 100	Red	
	panel F, H	chromogranin A (61-0015)	1: 400	Brown	
	panel J, K	CD45 (NCL-L-LCA)	1: 200	Brown	
	panel L, M	Ki-67 (61-0078)	1: 800	Brown	
	Suppl. Fig. S4	panel A, B, D	CD31 (MS-353-S1)	1: 100	Red
			D2-40 (916602)	1: 100	Green
Suppl. Video S1		glucagon (ab10988)	1: 100	Magenta	
		insulin-Alexa Fluor® 488 (sc-8033_AF488)	1: 100	Blue	
		CK7 (ab68459)	1: 100	Green	

Note: CK7 (epithelial marker); chromogranin A (neuroendocrine lesion marker); PGP9.5 (neuroendocrine marker for nerve, islet, and microadenoma labeling); CD31 (endothelial marker for blood vessel labeling); D2-40 (lymphatic endothelial marker for lymphatic vessel labeling); CD45 (leukocyte common antigen); Ki-67 (proliferation marker).